

CLASSROOM ACTIVITIES TO ENERGIZING JUNIOR GRADES

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Every teacher wants his subject to be interesting and useful. That's why the problem of raising students' motivation is relevant nowadays. The aim of the article is show how a teacher can motivate students to learn foreign languages with great pleasure. The study material is based on linguistic researchers, the Internet and educational sources. In our opinion this topic will be interesting for creative teachers who are motivated to achieve good results themselves. Motivation is a key element of class activity according to the learning standards in the Russian Federation where the personality of a student, his ability to self-knowledge, independence in decision-making is in the center of attention. Therefore the main task of the teacher following learning standards is increasing students' interest in foreign languages. It is impossible to teach the student who does not want to study as he does not know what it is necessary for and how to use the gained knowledge in life. Therefore the motivation cannot be considered only as a separate stage of a lesson within leaning standards, it is a fundamental stage of all lesson. Nowadays most schools face the problem of the absence of interest to study languages because many students consider foreign languages to be the most difficult subject. According to the statistics the reasons of the decrease of motivation are the following: the lack of interest to the subject, difficulties in pronunciation, grammar, the fear to communicate with foreigners, underestimated self-assessment, and students do not like to learn new words by heart and they do not really understand the importance of foreign languages in their future. Any school subject has enough opportunities for motivation of cognitive activity of students, and English is not an exception. The aim of a teacher is to raise students' interest and to show all the secrets of the subject with the help of own experience, knowledge, human qualities and enthusiasm. Nowadays there are a lot of ways and means of raising motivation at the lessons of foreign languages. One of the means of motivation is the Student's book. A teacher must use the opportunities of books, which contain a lot of relevant topics for discussion, colorful pictures, unusual tasks, ideas for team work and for projects, and give references to the video in the Internet. One more means of "awakening" interest among students is creation of a problem situation. In this case we notice that research activity is combined with inner

motivation, the ability to learn and create something new. This method allows maintaining the interest of school students in educational process throughout all lesson. Role game is also one of the means of increasing motivation as during the game, students do not pay attention to the fact that they study new material. Any game is much more interesting and more fascinating, than plain theoretical material and always creates the success situation. The games "Crocodile", "Snowball", "I Trust — I Do Not Believe", "linguistic (mathematical) soccer" can serve as examples of such games. The method of projects gives students some freedom, an opportunity to show their creativity and it promotes the competition where everyone tries to do the best. While making projects students use some extra information which can motivate students. The important means of raising motivation is using the Internet. Modern students can't live without gadgets and they will be interested in the material shown on the smart board. Besides, teachers can create web-quests where students have to do interactive tasks, watch videos, make podcasts or even investigations. The success at the lesson of foreign languages greatly depends on the forms of work organization during the lesson. A special role is played by a collective form of work when pupils should discuss together problems and find ways of their decision. Such form of work unites pupils, even the weakest children can participate without any fear of being mistaken. To make a conclusion, it is necessary to say that the high level of motivation serves as a success indicator in education that is why its achievement is one of the priority directions of learning standards. And the role of any teacher is very important – he has a great responsibility to make students learn the subject with pleasure and believe in their own abilities. And responsibility of the teacher is a intention for constant search, changes, flexibility in decision-making. Any bearing responsibility has to be rewarded, and an award for the teacher is motivated students.

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